

L. Lindgren 1977.12.04 (Note 14)

The purpose of this note is to point out the close relation between parallax determinations and thermal effects on the complex mirror. This is a consequence of that the thermal impact and the parallactic displacement of a star in the telescope reference frame both depend on the orientation of the Sun relative to the spacecraft.

The Sun-spacecraft geometry is completely specified by the two angles ζ and v (fig.). During one scan, the angle v goes from 0 to 2π , while ζ remains almost constant (note that this is not restricted to revolving scanning). With no eclipses and provided that the variation of ζ is so slow that dynamic effects are negligible, it can be assumed that the basic angle varies around its mean value γ_0 according to

$$\gamma = \gamma_0 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \{a_k(\zeta) \cos kv + b_k(\zeta) \sin kv\}. \quad (1)$$

To see how this influences the parallaxes, let us first study its effects on the measured positions of stars along a closed scanning great circle. Let w_i be the true position along the great circle of the i :th star, and $w_i + \Delta w_i$ the position measured with a varying basic angle. The relevant deterministic part of the observation equation for a connexion of two stars in the p and f fields is

$$\Delta w_p - \Delta w_f = - \sum_k (a_k \cos kv + b_k \sin kv), \quad (2)$$

where $v = (w_p + w_f)/2$. Putting

$$\Delta w_i = \sum_k (A_k \cos kw_i + B_k \sin kw_i) \quad (3)$$

and using the approximate positions $w_p = v + \gamma/2$, $w_f = v - \gamma/2$, we get the solution

$$A_k = \frac{b_k}{2 \sin(k\gamma/2)}, \quad B_k = - \frac{a_k}{2 \sin(k\gamma/2)}. \quad (4)$$

It can be shown that inclusion of p-p and f-f connections does not alter A_k , B_k very much.

The total parallactic displacement of a star at position w is $D = \tilde{\omega} \sin \eta$, where $\tilde{\omega}$ is the parallax. Its components along and normal to the scan are

$$D_{\parallel} = - \tilde{\omega} \sin \eta \sin \theta = - \tilde{\omega} \sin \zeta \sin w \quad (5a)$$

$$D_{\perp} = \tilde{\omega} \sin \eta \cos \theta \approx \tilde{\omega} \cos \zeta. \quad (5b)$$

The parallactic displacement of a star along the scan therefore varies sinusoidally with w (note that w is generally different for the different occasions when a certain star is observed), the amplitude being $\tilde{\omega} \sin \zeta$. (This is why we want to have ζ as big as possible.) Comparison with (3) and (4) shows that we can expect a parallax bias (i.e. a non-zero parallax for very distant stars) amounting to

$$\tilde{\omega}_0 = - \frac{B_1}{\sin \zeta} = \frac{a_1}{2 \sin \zeta \sin(\gamma/2)} \approx 1.5 a_1 \tag{6}$$

for $\zeta = 30^\circ$ and $\gamma = 84^\circ$.

A parallax bias means that only relative parallaxes (and not absolute) can be measured with the satellite. Høg (Note 19) has already pointed out that this is not a serious drawback, as $\tilde{\omega}_0$ can be very accurately determined from the vast number of stars in the observing program with such small parallaxes (≤ 0.005 ?) that their photometric distances are more accurate than their trigonometric distances will be. Instead, we require that the bias is constant and well-defined throughout the mission. As a_k, b_k will depend on ζ , this is an argument for keeping ζ as constant as possible (e.g. inclined or revolving scanning in the original senses). However, (6) indicates that a much larger variation of ζ is tolerable if $a_1 \approx \text{const.} \sin \zeta$, which may very well be the case.